

Research Article

Impact of Emerging Technologies on Economic and Social Performances of Hearing Impaired Persons in Ogun State

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Abstract

Those with hearing impairment are on the increase in our society due to factors such as undue exposure to prolonged high level of noise from various sources from infancy causing auditory neurological imbalance, aftermath of improperly treated diseases such as measles, resultant effect of fatal accidents and the side effects of certain prenatal or ante-natal therapies. These have rendered many otherwise useful individual useless. This study examined the effect of emerging technologies on combating hearing impairment challenges. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Using purposive and expert sampling techniques, a sample of 300 comprising of technology experts, hearing impaired persons and human rights activists was taken from Ogun State Nigeria. Simple percentage analysis and Chi square statistical tools were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that adoption of emerging technologies on Hearing Aids such as Cochlear Implant, Alerting device and Assistive Listening Devices (ALD) will improve economic and social performances of hearing impaired persons; there will be significantly better performance of persons with hearing impairment who adopt emerging technologies compared to those who do not; level of awareness of the requisite technology by persons with hearing impairment significantly enhances their chances of adopting emerging technologies. In view of the findings, it was apparent that people with hearing impairment can be as resourceful in our society as other citizens without any discrimination if advantage of appropriate emerging technology is taken. Government should do more to assist persons with hearing impairment to acquire the relevant technological devices to make them socially and

economically more relevant. Policy makers and curriculum reviewers in educational institutions, especially in special education departments should incorporate the training in the use of appropriate emerging technologies into their special education programs and instructions to meet the unique needs of students and pupils with hearing impairment.

KEYWORDS: Hearing Impaired, Emerging Technologies, Captioning, Sound Fields, Cochlear Implants.

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Introduction

Persons with hearing impairment and other disabilities are the most vulnerable and disadvantaged groups in the society (Onyema, 2016). They face many challenges and are often excluded, marginalized, forgotten and left behind in the society. Communication between hearing-impaired individuals and the normal-hearing individuals can be very difficult. It is often true that in school settings or class scenarios, the hearing-impaired individuals (students) are often involved in project-oriented groups; thus, miscommunication is normal between them and the normal hearing individuals (Norazah et al, 2015). However, the recent development of emerging technologies have the potential to meet these challenges and can also be used to increase the productivity, employment opportunities and development of important life skills for persons with disabilities (Nabil,2013). Emerging technologies can help improve learning opportunities for hearing-impaired individuals and to encourage their career pursuits.

Emerging Technology offer new opportunities for everyone, but these opportunities are specifically more significant for persons with Disabilities (PwDs), who use assistive technology for their daily activities to a higher extent than people in general. Today's assistive technology, which is adapted to everyone's abilities, means that disabled end users are able to participate in all aspects of social life on more equal terms than ever before. It is vital that people are able to benefit on an equal basis from the rapid development of emerging technology, to enable them to partake in an inclusive and barrier-free information society (Nabil, 2013). Technology provides disabled persons with an improved quality of life and offers the possibility of accessing knowledge by adapting digital media to the nature of their disabilities. According to the Japanese Society for Rehabilitation of Persons with Disabilities (2007), emerging Technology (ET) offer persons with disabilities new possibilities to achieve independent living and full participation in social, economic, and cultural activities. Thus, individuals with serious sensory disabilities such as hearing impairments or deafness have benefited more than any other group of individuals from advances in emerging technologies (Nabil, 2013).

The description of a person's hearing loss is often based on their level of hearing at different frequencies as measured by an audiologist (Stacie, 2009). Hearing loss levels are often broadly described as mild, moderate, severe and profound. Generalizations based on these single word descriptors often do not accurately predict an individual's skills across a variety of tasks such as speech, language, listening, communication mode, etc. The terminology "deaf" and "hard of hearing" used to describe individuals with hearing impairment is based on a medical model and definition of hearing loss levels. How an individual views him/herself, however, can depend on self-identity and cultural values related to or separate from the status of their hearing. For example, a person who has a level of hearing that may be medically described as hard of hearing (a person diagnosed with a "moderate" or "severe" hearing loss) may actually identify him/herself as Deaf based on their preferred communication mode, cultural values, and self-identity. Regardless of definition, hearing impaired people do not support the use of negative descriptors such as hearing loss, deafness, impairment, or disability.

Hearing impaired individuals utilize a variety of emerging and assistive technologies that provide them with improved accessibility in numerous environments. Most devices either provide amplified sound or alternate ways to access information through vision and/or vibration. These technologies can be grouped into three general categories: hearing technology; alerting devices; and communication supports. Within each main category there may be subcategories based on different purposes or intended audiences when utilizing the technology. These technologies can enhance the lives of individuals who are hearing as well as individuals with deafness or hearing impairment. Some of these technologies that are of specific interest to professionals, families, and individuals with hearing impairment include: hearing aids, telecommunication devices for the deaf (TDD), closed captioning, real-time captioning, sound fields, FM systems, speech and speech reading computer programs, computer assisted note-taking, cochlear implants, and the Internet (John, 2014).

Emerging technology has the potential for multifarious uses for and by persons with disabilities (Misako *et al.*, 2007). For the hearing impaired, it can provide direct access to visual images and source of information and means of instant communication. With additional gadgets for sound production and Braille printing, it can be at the service of the visually handicapped persons. It can be used by persons with severe physical disability and severe speech problems as the means of communication. It has been used for speech training of persons with mental retardation through relevant games and exercises. However, despite the concerted efforts over the years to meet the challenges of hearing impairment, there still exist some gaps in the literature on meeting the challenges

of hearing impairment with emerging technology. Consequently, this study is aimed to examine ways by which emerging (assistive) technology that can further help hearing impaired individuals to overcome their challenges across a variety of environments. The outcome would help to promote social inclusion and education of persons with disabilities (PwDs).

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to find ways of combating hearing impairment challenges using emerging technologies. Other specific objectives are to:

- (i) review the existing literatures on the subject matter;
- (ii) examine the challenges of hearing impairment;
- (iii) identify relevant emerging technologies for hearing impairment;
- (iv) To identify impediments to adoption of relevant emerging technologies helpful to the hearing impaired.

Research Hypotheses

- H0₁:** Use and Adoption of Emerging Technologies have no positive impact on persons with Hearing impairment.
- H0₂:** There is no significant performance difference between persons with hearing impairment who adopt Emerging Technologies and those who do not
- H0₃:** The awareness level of persons with hearing impairment has a positive impact on their adoption of emerging technologies

Literature Review

Persons with disabilities (PwDs) are the most vulnerable and disadvantaged groups in the society (Onyema, 2016). They face many challenges and are often excluded, marginalized, forgotten and left behind in the facets of societal activities. Disability comes in different forms such as; visual impairment, hearing impairment and physical disability. Hearing impairment which is the major concern of this study presents a direct physical obstacle to communication. The inability to communicate well with others can lead to isolation and depression, and impacts everyday life in many ways. Unfortunately, in the recent past, the society does not take into consideration the needs of people with hearing impairment, thereby making the world less accessible to them and compounding their difficulties and challenges. However, the recent development in emerging technologies have the potential to meet these challenges and can also be used to promote the education and to increase the employment opportunities and development of important life skills for persons with disabilities (Nabil,2013). Technology offer persons

with disabilities new possibilities to achieve independent living and full participation in social, educational, economic, and cultural activities.

Hearing is the ability to perceive sound. A person suffering from hearing impairment has difficulty in perceiving or identifying sound clearly due to auditory problems. The impairment may be unilateral or bilateral. Being deaf or hard of hearing affects people in various ways, depending upon the nature of the hearing impairment, personal circumstances, additional medical problems and the presence or absence of support. However, in all cases, many communication problems can be reduced by ensuring the environment is acoustically friendly.

The modern world presents many challenges of very different types. Our senses are constantly being assailed with new sensations, environments, and experiences. We have to develop coping strategies that allow us to move with confidence and deal with these challenges without becoming overwhelmed. For many of us, that is a significant task. For others, particularly those with a disability, it is a monumental challenge. Deafness is often described as 'the silent disability' because it is not noticed, not visible and not discussed, yet it is a condition growing in importance and prevalence.

People who are hard of hearing have to cope with hearing impairment every day, in many challenging hearing environments. They face obstacles in most areas of their lives some of which in:

Education Settings: Miscommunication can result in poor grades. Educators can be unaware that students have not heard the correct instructions, and mislabel children with hearing loss as 'lazy' or 'stupid'. Many people with hearing impairment do not achieve a high level of education, even if they have attended school for a few years. They have limited access to mainstream education as well as technical and vocational education or training. Teachers in formal and non-formal training centres have often not been trained in inclusive education. Frequently, sign language and teaching methodologies have not been adapted to the needs of students with hearing impairment. This situation limits the quality of teaching and practical exchanges between students and teachers. The majority of training structures also lack training material, clear curricula, and tools linked to sign language.

Workplace: People with hearing loss have more difficulty in finding employment and struggle with certain practical aspects, such as attending group meetings or answering

the telephone. They often discriminated against in work places and isolated sometimes. This affects them directly and indirectly.

Social Situations: Hearing people cannot see that a person with hearing loss has difficulty hearing others, and also forget that hearing aids and cochlear implants are only aids. They need to be constantly reminded to consider the hearing difficulty, which can be tiring, frustrating and embarrassing. It can become easier for a person with hearing loss to withdraw from social events and isolate themselves. For this and other reasons, people seldom admit they have a hearing loss and it usually takes them seven to ten years to do something about it. By the time they take action and consult a health worker, they have long struggled to keep up with what is being spoken about at home, socially and in the workplace. People who are deaf or hard of hearing are not due to their hearing impairment alone, but are greatly compounded by social attitudes and lack of access. By considering the practical needs of people who are deaf or hard of hearing and acknowledging their potential, we can become a more inclusive society.

Methodology

This study was conducted using a descriptive research design. The target population comprised Technology experts, Hearing impaired persons, Human rights group and researchers from Ogun State, Nigeria. Purposive and Expert sampling techniques were used to select the sample size of three hundred (300) respondents for the study. Questionnaire was used as primary instrument to gather relevant data for this study. Simple percentage and Chi-square were used to analyze the data gathered.

Results

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the Challenges of persons with Hearing Impairment?

Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, and Q5 are related to this research question. Responses obtained to them from the respondents are presented in the following frequency distribution table.

Table 1: Persons with hearing impairment face steady challenges and difficulties including neglect and stigmatization due to their inability to utilize a sense organ (eyes) which also affect their movement and daily life activities

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	150	150	50
	A	80	230	27
	D	40	270	13
	SD	30	300	10
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 1 shows that 77% of the respondents agreed that persons with hearing impairment face steady challenges and difficulties including neglect and stigmatization due to their inability to utilize a sense organ (eyes) which also affect their movement and daily life activities while 23% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 2: Persons with hearing impairment are sexually abused and lack the physical energy to fight sexual aggressors or the voice to report assault or abuse cases

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	180	180	60
	A	70	250	23
	D	30	280	10
	SD	20	300	7
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 2 shows that 83% of the respondents agreed that Persons with hearing impairment are sexually abused and lack the physical energy to fight sexual aggressors or the voice to report assault or abuse cases while 17% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 3: Persons with hearing impairment are excluded from educational opportunities due to their impairment

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	150	150	50
	A	80	230	27
	D	40	270	13
	SD	30	300	10
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 3 shows that 77% of the respondents agreed that Persons with hearing impairment are excluded from educational opportunities due to their impairment while 23% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 4: There is a high rate of unemployment among Persons with hearing impairment because they are denied employment due to their disability

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	200	200	67
	A	60	260	20
	D	25	285	8
	SD	15	300	5
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 4 shows that 87% of the respondents agreed that there is a high rate of unemployment among Persons with hearing impairment because they are denied employment due to their disability while 13% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 5: Persons with hearing impairment face countless discrimination in the society and are often excluded in social activities?

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	150	250	50
	A	50	200	17
	D	60	260	20
	SD	40	300	13
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 5 shows that 67% of the respondents agreed that Persons with hearing impairment face countless discrimination in the society and are often excluded in social activities while 33% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Research Question 2: What are the emerging technologies that can be used to meet the challenges of persons with Hearing Impairment?

Q6, Q7, Q8, Q9, and Q9 are related to this research question. Responses obtained to them from the respondents are presented in the following frequency distribution table.

Table 6: Hearing Aids such as Cochlear Implant and Alerting devices amplify sound to assist persons with hearing impairment

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	180	180	60
	A	70	250	23
	D	30	280	10
	SD	20	300	7
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 6 shows that 83% of the respondents agreed that hearing aids such as Cochlear Implant and Alerting devices amplify sound to assist persons with hearing impairment while 17% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 7:The use of internet or electronic learning technologies can encourage the education of persons with hearing impairment through online learning channels or platform

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	150	150	50
	A	80	230	27
	D	40	270	13
	SD	30	300	10
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 7 shows that 77% of the respondents agreed that the use of internet or electronic learning technologies can encourage the education of persons with hearing impairment through online learning channels or platform while 23% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 8: Alerting devices provide an amplified or visual signal or vibration used to get the attention of persons with hearing impairment

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	200	200	67
	A	60	260	20
	D	25	285	8
	SD	15	300	5
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 8 shows that 87% of the respondents agreed that Alerting devices provide an amplified or visual signal or vibration used to get the attention of persons with hearing impairment while 13% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 9: Assistive Listening Devices (ALD) such as personal Amplifier can be used to improve the hearing ability of persons with hearing impairment

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	150	250	50
	A	50	200	17
	D	60	260	20
	SD	40	300	13
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 9 shows that 67% of the respondents agreed that Assistive Listening Devices (ALD) such as personal Amplifier can be used to improve the hearing ability of persons with hearing impairment while 33% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 10: Sign language Recognition device can be used by persons with hearing impairment to understand sign languages

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	150	150	50
	A	80	230	27
	D	40	270	13
	SD	30	300	10
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 10 shows that 77% of the respondents agreed that Sign language Recognition device can be used by persons with hearing impairment to understand sign languages while 23% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Research Question 3: What are the impediments to adoption of emerging technologies? Q11, Q12, Q13, Q14, and Q15 are related to this research question. Responses obtained to them from the respondents are presented in the following frequency distribution table.

Table 11: Adoption of Emerging technologies can be hindered by lack of awareness about the its potential and values

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	200	200	67
	A	60	260	20
	D	25	285	8
	SD	15	300	5
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 11 shows that 87% of the respondents agreed that Adoption of Emerging technologies can be hindered by lack of awareness about the it’s potential and values while 13% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 12: Assistive Technology devices are expensive and not affordable for persons with hearing impairment

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	220	220	73
	A	50	270	17
	D	20	290	7
	SD	10	300	3
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 12 shows that 90% of the respondents agreed that Assistive Technology devices are expensive and not affordable for persons with hearing impairment while 10% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 13: Availability and accessibility may prove barrier to the adoption of Emerging Technologies by persons with hearing impairment

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	240	240	80
	A	20	260	7
	D	25	285	8
	SD	15	300	5
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 13 shows that 87% of the respondents agreed that Availability and accessibility may prove barrier to the adoption of emerging technologies by persons with hearing impairment while 13% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 14: Illiteracy or poor training on usage of emerging technology devices may hinder its adoption by persons with hearing impairment or other form of disabilities

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	230	230	77
	A	20	250	7
	D	28	278	9
	SD	22	300	7
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 14 shows that 84% of the respondents agreed that Availability and accessibility may prove barrier to the adoption of Emerging Technologies by persons with hearing impairment while 16% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Table 15: Stigmatization may affect the adoption of emerging technology devices by persons with Hearing Impairment

		Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage
Valid	SA	150	250	50
	A	50	200	17
	D	60	260	20
	SD	40	300	13
Total		300		100

Source: Field Survey, 2017.

Table 15 shows that 77% of the respondents agreed that Stigmatization may affect the adoption of emerging technology devices by persons with hearing impairment while 23% of the respondents disagreed with this claim.

Test of Research Hypotheses

H₀: Use and Adoption of Emerging Technologies have no positive impact on persons with Hearing impairment.

H₁: Use and Adoption of Emerging Technologies have a positive impact on persons with Hearing impairment.

The result of the chi-square analysis is presented below to test whether the null hypothesis should be accepted or the alternative hypothesis.

Table 16 shows the Chi-Square analysis of the impact of use and adoption of emerging technologies on Persons with Hearing Impairment.

Table 16: Ho: Use and Adoption of Emerging Technologies have no positive impact on persons with Hearing impairment.

Responses	Observed value	Expected value	Df	X ² - calculated	X ² - critical value	P	Decision
SA	329	375.0	3	29.627	7.815	0.05	Accept the Alternative Hypothesis
A	428	375.0					
D	316	375.0					
SD	427	375.0					

Table 16 shows the Chi-square summary, it shows that the calculated X^2 -statistics is 262.992 while the critical value is 7.815 and 5% level of significance with 3 as the degree of freedom. The rule of thumb guiding the acceptability of a particular hypothesis in chi-square states that when the X^2 -calculated is greater than X^2 -critical, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, since the condition was certified as the calculated value is greater than the critical value. Hence, we rejected the null hypothesis which states that Use and Adoption of Emerging Technologies have no positive impact on persons with Hearing impairment. This implies that the use and adoption of emerging technologies have positive effects on persons with disabilities.

Testing of Hypothesis Two

H0₂: There is no significant performance difference between persons with Hearing Impairment who adopt Emerging Technologies and those who do not.

Table 17: The chi-square analysis of the difference between persons with Hearing Impairment who adopt Emerging Technologies and those who do not

Responses	Observed value	Expected value	D f	X^2 -calculated	X^2 -critical value	P	Decision
SA	329	375.0	3	29.627	7.815	0.05	Reject the null Hypothesis
A	428	375.0					
D	316	375.0					
SD	427	375.0					

Table 17 shows the chi-square summary that the calculated X^2 -statistics is 29.627 while the critical value is 7.815 at 5% level of significance with 3 as the degree of freedom. Since the X^2 -calculated is greater than X^2 -critical, we rejected the null hypothesis. Hence, we conclude that there is a significant difference between persons with Hearing Impairment who adopt Emerging Technologies and those who do not. Hence, we rejected the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant performance difference between persons with Hearing Impairment who adopt Emerging Technologies and those who do not.

Testing of Hypothesis Three

Table 18: H0₃: Level of awareness of persons with hearing impairment has no positive impact on their adoption of emerging technologies

Responses	Observed value	Expected value	Df	X ² – calculated	X ² - critical value	P	Decision
SA	368	375.0	3	98.107	7.815	0.05	Reject the null Hypothesis
A	512	375.0					
D	379	375.0					
SD	241	375.0					

Table 18 shows the chi-square summary that the calculated X²-statistics is 98.107 while the critical value is 7.815 at 5% level of significance with 3 as the degree of freedom. Since the X²-calculated is greater than X² Critical, we rejected the null hypothesis. Hence, we conclude that the awareness level of persons with hearing impairment has no positive impact on their adoption of emerging technologies. This implies that poor awareness of persons with hearing impairment has effects on their adoption of emerging technologies. Hence an increase in the awareness level of emerging technologies can lead to a corresponding increase in adoption of emerging technologies by persons with hearing impairment.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the results from these analyses, it was found from the results of the tested hypotheses that use and adoption of emerging technologies will have significant positive effect on persons with hearing impairment; that there is a statistically significant difference in performance between persons with Hearing Impairment who adopt emerging technologies and those who do not. This study also revealed that awareness level of persons with hearing impairment has effects on their adoption of emerging technologies. This implies that an increase in the awareness level of persons with hearing impairment can lead to a corresponding increase in adoption of emerging technologies.

This study has shown that persons with hearing impairment are faced with different challenges ranging from deprivations, discriminations and sexual abuse. However, the evolution of emerging technologies has provided different assistive devices that can be used to meet many of these challenges in order to assist persons with hearing impairment and indeed other forms of disabilities to live a better life. The result further shows that

lack of awareness, cost of emerging technological devices and accessibility factors could hinder the adoption of emerging technologies by persons with hearing impairment.

Conclusion

Technology lies at the heart of most aspects of inclusive development and the fulfillment of rights for persons with disabilities. Without technology, basic rights such as access to education and employment and participation in social, cultural and political aspects of society cannot be realized for persons with disabilities. Making the benefits of technology accessible, is an essential component to realizing the rights of persons with disabilities and ensuring they are included in development. Often, and particularly in developing countries, developments in technology are too expensive or exclusive and are therefore not used as enablers to promote inclusive development.

Policy-makers and the market need to ensure that existing and new technologies are made accessible to those groups who are often excluded from the benefits of mainstream technological developments, particularly persons with disabilities. Approaches to technology innovations need to shift from current attitudes whereby the benefits of technology are only occasionally provided to persons with disabilities as a by-product of mainstream developments, to an approach that more systematically advances and promotes the transformative potential of technology for persons with disabilities. The benefits of technology need to be translated into an inclusive development agenda at the same pace as technology advancements and innovations. Special efforts are required to address this challenge and to strengthen accessibility of appropriate and socially-just technologies.

Considering the positive impact of emerging technologies on persons with disabilities particularly on persons with hearing impairment, there is a distinct need for researchers, practitioners, and other stakeholders in the system to identify ways to encourage the development of tools and strategies for technology integration, and strive to work together on issues surrounding the use of technology, for effective inclusion of students with disabilities within the general education environment, ensuring that they are entitled to the same high standards and effective instruction that is available to the non-disabled students. It is essential to focus and build on the strengths and capabilities of the students, with the necessary support and assistance, to give more room to their abilities in order to address their 'disabilities.

Finally, while there have been a large number of successful individuals who are deaf or hard of hearing, there also have been far too many persons with a hearing loss who have not received a quality education, shared positive relationships, or had satisfying careers. Hopefully, the future will be filled with less controversy and increased successes through the use of emerging technologies. Hopefully, there will be a heightened understanding that all human beings, whether they have a hearing loss or not, are diverse, complex and have specific needs that must be met for optimum development to occur. Hopefully, people will work in partnership to make this a better world for people who are deaf, hard of hearing, or hearing impaired to live and succeed.

Recommendations

- In view of the findings, the recommendations are hereby suggested:
- (i) Hearing impaired individuals in our society should be give equal rights to participate in utilising ICT infrastructures in our society as other citizens without any discrimination.
 - (ii) Government, industries, private individuals, NGOs and the like should do more to assist persons with hearing impairment to acquire the relevant technological devices to aid their activities.
 - (iii) There should be an increased awareness of ICT for persons with disabilities.
 - (iv) Policy makers and authorities in educational institutions should develop special-education programs and instructions to meet the unique needs of students with hearing impairment at no cost to the child or the child's parents.

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